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National Interest as Basis of National Security of Ukraine in Modern Geopolitical Space

У статті розглянуто проблематику національних інтересів як основи національної безпеки України у сучасних геополітичних умовах. Наголошено, що національний інтерес має ретроспективний характер, адже він формується під впливом історичних процесів та особливостей становлення суспільства та держави. Підкреслено, що в Україні явище «національний інтерес» набуло актуальності після розпаду СРСР в 90-х рр. минулого століття. Розкрито особливості співвідношення національних інтересів та національної безпеки. Визначено первинні загрози для національних інтересів України на сучасному етапі.

Ключові слова: національні інтереси, національна безпека, громадянське суспільство, правова держава, геополітика, глобалізація.

В статье рассмотрена проблематика национальных интересов как основы национальной безопасности Украины в современных геополитических условиях. Отмечено, что национальный интерес имеет ретроспективный характер, ведь он формируется под влиянием исторических процессов и особенностей становления общества и государства. Подчеркнуто, что в Украине явление «национальный интерес» приобрел актуальность после распада СССР в 90-х гг. прошлого века. Раскрыты особенности соотношения национальных интересов и национальной безопасности. Определены первичные угрозы для национальных интересов Украины на современном этапе.

Ключевые слова: национальные интересы, национальная безопасность, гражданское общество, правовое государство, геополитика, глобализация.

In the article the problems of national interests as the basis of national security of Ukraine in modern geopolitical conditions are considered. It is emphasised that the national interest has a retrospective character, as it is formed under the influence of historical processes and peculiarities of the formation of society and the state. It is stressed that in Ukraine the phenomenon of national interest became relevant after the collapse of the USSR in the 90s of the last century. National interest is a complex and integrative political and legal phenomenon. National interest has a retrospective nature, as it is formed under the influence of historical processes and peculiarities of the development of society and the state – as a result, in the content of national interest there 1) either the progress of the previous stage is traced clearly and consistently; 2) or the opposite vector of development is chosen, which is usually related to the refusal from the undemocratic form of the state regime. In Ukraine, the phenomenon of national interest became relevant after the collapse of the USSR in the 90s of the last century.

The features of the interrelation of national interest and national security are revealed. In science, discussions on the relationship between the concepts of “national security” and “national interests” continue. National interests are the main interests and needs of individuals, societies and states that define the conditions and form a standard of living in it. National security is a complex cross-sectoral system aimed at ensuring conditions for the realization of these needs and interests, and if necessary, for their protection. National interests are permanent in character and vary depending on both internal factors and external ones. The primary threats to Ukraine’s national interest at the present stage are identified.

Keywords: national interests, national security, civil society, rule of law, geopolitics, globalization.

In today's geopolitical and globalized conditions, the issue of national security is of particular importance. In its turn, the establishment and consolidation of national interests as the basis of national security of Ukraine is a key task of the individual, society and the state. It is the formation and realization of national interests that serve as the primary element of strengthening Ukrainian statehood.

The category of national interest has become even more important in recent years, and has become increasingly used in various spheres of life and various subjects. Currently, national interests are the leading direction in the activities of public authorities, public organizations, political structures. However, both the beginning of the twenty-first century and the present is characterized by lack of comprehension of Ukraine's national interests. Therefore, understanding and realization of the national interests of our country requires the objectivity of the view and monitoring of positive and, above all, negative factors of the current transformation processes in Ukraine and in the world.

Analysis of Publications. The problems of national interests from the standpoint of different sciences were studied by such domestic and foreign scholars as R. Aron, V. Bilous, Yu. Bytiak, V. Bielievitseva, S. Bondarenko, V. Vovk, A. Vozgennykov, K. Gadzhiev, V. Garashchuk, G. Glezerman, V. Gorbulin, O. Dzioban, G. Dugin, S. Zdioruk, A. Zdravomyslov, A. Kachynskiy, J. Kennan, S. Cohen, A. Kolodii, C. Lerch, A. Lytvynenko, B. Lipkan, V. Manzhola, V. Madisson, B. Mezhuev, M. Mykhalchenko, M. Molchanov, H. Morgenthau, L. Nalyvaiko, V. Nastiuik, O. Ovchynnikova, G. Pozdniakov, F. Ratzel, J. Rosenau, F. Rudych, A. Said, G. Sytnyk, N. Spikeman, V. Truhachov, S. Huntington, R. Kjellen, V. Shahov, L. Shypilova, S. Spiegel, I. Yakovenko and many others.

Studies of national interests were carried out within the philosophy, sociology, political science, public administration science, history, and so on. However, lawyers do not pay enough attention to this issue. Most legal research is aimed at studying the categories of interest, legal interest, legitimate interest, etc. Taking into account the present complex state of ensuring national security, the study of Ukraine's national interest has a special applied and theoretical significance, in particular from the

point of view of administrative law, since national interests are expressed through the purpose and tasks of the political and legal activity of the state and are realized primarily by the public administration through its management function.

The purpose of the article is the administrative legal characteristic of the content of the category of national interests, the disclosure of its interconnection and interdependence with the provision of national security of the state in the current globalization conditions.

Presenting main material. The complexity of further predicting the formation of national interests and national security determines, inter alia, the application of interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral approaches.

National interest is a key concept in international relations. Every nation is always engaged in the process of fulfilling or securing the goals of its national interests. The foreign policy of each nation is formed on the basis of its national interests and always works to ensure its goals. This is the general right of every state to safeguard its national interests. The state always tries to justify its actions on the basis of national interests. The behaviour of the state is conditioned and guided by its national interests [1]. Therefore, the question of the content filling of the term "national interests" is important for the process of their implementation at the national and international levels.

Today Ukrainian society is characterized by a crisis of value-ideological foundations, which manifests itself in the loss of moral standards, growth in deviant behaviour, an increase in the dispersion and differentiation of Ukrainian society. This crisis can be overcome by reassessing the former norms and creating on this basis a new system of values [2, p. 465]. Taking into account the above, the problem of studying national interests, in particular, in the context of their interdependence with the provision of national security, is of great importance for the further development of Ukrainian statehood.

National interests, in the retrospective aspect, are one of the main categories in the science of the countries of Western Europe and the United States of America.

In western political literature, the term "national interest" was defined as "state interest". It is this understanding that prevails in the western countries, since they are mostly monotonous states (not so much in the ethnic aspect as in the social one).

In Western societies, a nation is a unity of civil society and state, so national interest fulfills consolidating function and reduces contradictions between the interests of the state and civil society [2, p. 466]. In Ukraine, the phenomenon of national interest became relevant after the collapse of the USSR in the 90s of the last century. Today, this category is widely distributed in various fields and spheres of life. However, the versatility of the interpretation of the term “national interests” negatively affects the practical part of its implementation and doctrinal positions in the domestic spaces. It should be emphasised that in transitional societies, including Ukraine, it is inappropriate to fully identify the categories of national interest and public interest, although they are certainly interconnected and coincide in a number of aspects. Equating these phenomena can be somewhere dangerous for society, since in this case there are manipulations on the part of political actors.

Another significant problem is the definition of the interrelation between the terms “national interests” and “national security”.

In the modern world scientific paradigm, there is a wide range of approaches to understanding the essence of national security. The ambiguity of understanding the main key categories of this problem acquires a particularly negative meaning. O. Dzioban emphasises that when formulating the category of national interests, the majority of theoreticians included it in the category of national security, giving the latter decisive significance, in the future these two categories allegedly merged into one [3, p. 124]. Nowadays, scientists continue to engage in heated discussions about the correlation of these phenomena.

Thus, V. Lipkan stresses that many researchers focus on the problem of broad interpretation of the categories “national security” and “national interests”, which actually leads to substitution of another category, for example, “function of the state”, as well as the merging of their subjects. The most popular and logical is the understanding that national interests are a broader category than national security. In turn, national security is not only an instrument for satisfying national interests, but also one of vital national interests, according to the author’s opinion [4, p. 42].

In turn, O. Turchenko point out that regardless of the level of security – national, regional, international – the object of its support is

always the interests of a particular subject, and today often the interests of one subject are replaced by the interests of another [5, p. 61-66]. In particular, the scientist considers the national interests as an object of national security.

The author also emphasises that national interest in the conditions of globalization is sometimes replaced by humanitarian interests or interests of the “international community”. However, the hopes for such an interest in the conditions of globalization are in vain, since there is no nation state capable of sacrificing its interests for the sake of the interests of other states, while it does not pursue other strategic goals [5, p. 66]. It should be stressed that the emergence and formation of national interests is an objective process, the basis of which are political, economic, cultural and other social relations.

According to I. Shevchuk, national interests are the fundamental notion of state policy on the implementation of national security, the goals of foreign and domestic policy, the direction of European integration aspirations and the protection of the interests of the nation [6, p. 18]. In accordance with this approach, national security can be understood as a logical and rational phenomenon that exists to ensure national interests.

Within the scope of this study, it is important to refer specifically to the national legislation, which defines these categories.

In particular, according to the Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine” of June 21, 2018, the national security of Ukraine is the protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, democratic constitutional order and other national interests of Ukraine from real and potential threats. In turn, the legislator suggests that under the national interests of Ukraine we should understand vital interests of man, society and the state, the realization of which ensures state sovereignty of Ukraine, its progressive democratic development, as well as safe living conditions and welfare of its citizens [7]. Accordingly, it should be noted that national interests are the main interests and needs of individuals and societies that determine the conditions and form a standard of living in the state, and national security is a complex cross-sectoral system aimed at ensuring conditions for the realization of these needs and interests, and if necessary, their protection.

National interests are the real reason for the actions of the nation and the state aimed at their survival, functioning and development, or a set of national goals and basic values that play an important role in national security strategies and tactics [8, p. 116]. B. Kormych observes that the category of national interests is systemic in the sense that, on the one hand, it forms the basis for defining the goals and directions of state policy and the activities of public authorities and the political system as a whole, and, on the other hand, the very content of national interests is formed in the process of development of the state and society under the influence of external and internal objective factors; all the institutions of the state, society, individual citizens are involved in the formation of the content of national interests. The basis of national interests is the triple system, which includes the national idea, the main goals and aspirations (needs) of society [9, p. 72-73]. A. Kuzmenko remarks that national interest is the determining source for the formation of the strategic goal, strategic objectives, the object of directions of the nation's development, methods and forms of their implementation, which focuses on the survival and progressive development, and, to a certain extent, the leadership of the individual, society, state [10]. It should be noted that today the content of Ukraine's national interests and the forms and methods of their implementation are under the influence of international transformation.

F. Medvid states that national interests should be regarded as internal, while the external interests are national-state. He believes that the main national interest for the nation as a political entity is to preserve its identity and cultural and linguistic identity. According to the scholar, the structural elements of national interest are the strengthening of economic power and the basis of their internal resources, the growth and rational use of national wealth, the harmonious development of productive forces operating in the country, the protection of territorial integrity, as well as the development of culture and language [11, p. 52-53]. Such an opinion of the author is quite fair, in particular, due to internal and external conflicts in Ukraine.

In determining the system of national interests of Ukraine one should take into account both the historical experience of national and state development, as well as all aspects of the modern geopolitical, historical and cultural, civilizational situation. In view of this the Ukrainian state should

develop its own model orientation in the universe, must have its own view of what's happening in the world, near and distant environment with which it interacts as an independent subject of international relations [12, p. 47]. At the same time, in science there is a modern view according to which interests are long-term standards that can characterize, evaluate political decisions and actions. Modern connections between interests and the national state are a product of history and, therefore, they can change their configuration. The connection between national interests and their product – the state – may eventually disappear. Political realism does not deny that the current division of the world into national states can be replaced by unions of states or other entities [13]. So today the Ukrainian state must more than ever activate toward making possible concepts, strategies and models of their existence in the world and build mutually beneficial relationships with other subjects of international law in partnership.

As scientists point out, world transformation is becoming the decisive form of the development of the modern world. It has an objective nature and is characterized by the fact that different parts of the world are in this interaction caused by thickening and intensifying interaction in all spheres of human life that shapes the world in a more coherent system. The world transformation differs by diffusion of economic, political and cultural processes, agglomeration of regional economic complexes and their political structures [14, p. 4]. In this regard, we can conclude that the national interests of each state have objective and subjective components, since they are formed by identifying global trends in different spheres and its own system of values, interests and needs. This provides an opportunity to define national interests as an objective-subjective phenomenon.

S. Bondarenko rightly states that today Ukraine is a territory of world confrontation, in which the political, social, humanitarian, cultural, economic, military interests of other states are realized. One of the strategic goals of world leaders is to control the information and communication space in spite of the national interests of other nations. It provides external access, development of necessary decisions and behavioral constructs of the population of territories under their influence. The danger of the situation is the application of new information and communication technologies that have a multipurpose purpose, allow us to form a new

value and ideological space of the world [15, p. 4]. The threat of such a situation is seen in the use of new information and communication technologies, which the Ukrainian state at the present stage is not always ready to oppose, due to the imperfection of information and communication technologies. In addition, it is the latest technology of individual international actors which is aimed at creating other moral and value realities in Ukrainian society, thereby transforming the spiritual and cultural component of society.

When it comes to society as a structured whole, it means, first of all, the ability of various legal social groups to effectively influence the actions of the authorities. The lack of a structured society greatly impedes the development of national identity. As a result, it is extremely difficult to articulate national interest and adequately represent and protect it in conditions of international competition of states [16, p. 157]. National interest is the result of mutually complex needs and interests of individuals of different social groups, society and the state, which should be the basis for decision-making public and should influence the state apparatus if necessary. Specifically, it requires political and legal education and maturity of public institutions – both state-owned and municipal as well as public.

In addition to the above, main indicators of internal threats and dangers for political and legal stability in Ukraine is the alienation of people from power, the substitution of the people's interests with vested interests of certain groups, the evolution of democratic to authoritarianism institutions, antagonization of public relations towards socially unjust course of reforms in society, subordination of mass media, unfair distribution of property and power, corruption of the apparatus of state administration, etc. [17, p. 111]. Consequently, the national interests of Ukraine, which now need urgent awareness of the society and the state, can be met only through a unified national strategy and taking into account the needs and interests of the whole society, not only of some influential groups.

Conclusions. Summing up the results of the research on the issues of national interests, we note the following.

1. National interest is a complex and integrative political and legal phenomenon. National interest has a retrospective nature, as it is formed under the influence of historical processes and

peculiarities of the development of society and the state – as a result, in the content of national interest there 1) either the progress of the previous stage is traced clearly and consistently; 2) or the opposite vector of development is chosen, which is usually related to the refusal from the undemocratic form of the state regime. In Ukraine, the phenomenon of national interest became relevant after the collapse of the USSR in the 90s of the last century. Today, this category is widely distributed in various fields and spheres of life. In transitional societies, including Ukraine, it is inappropriate to fully identify the notion of “national interest” and “state interest” (commonly used in Western democracies), although they are clearly interconnected and coincide in a number of respects. Equating these phenomena can be somewhere dangerous for society, since in this case there are manipulations on the part of political actors.

2. In science, discussions on the relationship between the concepts of “national security” and “national interests” continue. National interests are the main interests and needs of individuals, societies and states that define the conditions and form a standard of living in it. National security is a complex cross-sectoral system aimed at ensuring conditions for the realization of these needs and interests, and if necessary, for their protection. National interests are permanent in character and vary depending on both internal factors and external ones. The analysis of different points of view provides an opportunity to state the unconditional relationship and interdependence of these phenomena, but in the vast majority of cases, an approach to understanding national security as a multi-vector means of ensuring national interests is adhered to.

3. At the present stage, Ukrainian state continues to define and reflect on its own national interests. Globalization and the transformation of relations at the international level have a significant impact on this process. Among the primary threats to the national interests of Ukraine at the present stage are: the multiplicity of national interests of different countries of the world, which sometimes contradict Ukrainian national interests in the international arena: this requires clarification of the national interests of Ukraine and the possibilities and necessity of their realization in the modern geopolitical space; transboundary threats for the national interests of Ukraine; not always unity in the

commonality of the needs and interests of various individuals and social entities, in some cases their inadequate political and legal consciousness, which complicates the realization of national interests; mediated quality of the national information protection system; the lack of a fully-fledged and effective civil society, since society is a condition for the existence of any state and, without active support and public participation in the functioning of the state, it is almost unrealistic to ensure the national

interests of the whole country. Institutions of civil society primarily help to identify the needs and interests of the entire society; a variety of regional needs, determined by demographic, social, geographical, political and other factors. However, the distinction between these or other advantages or disadvantages of different regions should not be predominant in defining general needs and interests – national interests of the whole state, etc.

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